

Biomedical KG Construction Survey

Creation Date: 05/20/2020

This survey is meant to be used to collect information needed to compare PheKnowLator to existing biomedical knowledge graph construction methods.

While it is not feasible to implement and computationally compare existing methods to PheKnowLator, a detailed survey of existing methods is performed. To provide a fair comparison, no assumptions are made regarding a specific set of user requirements, instead, the focus of the survey is to provide a detailed overview of existing methods. With that in mind, the following 5 criteria were used to compare biomedical KG construction methods: (1) KG Construction Coverage; (2) Maturity; (3) Availability; (4) Usability; and (5) Reproducibility.

These criteria were loosely adapted from the following article: 10.1109/ASWEC.2004.1290484

* Required

1. Please enter today's date *

Example: January 7, 2019

2. Method name

3. Provide citation and/or link to the method

4. Primary goal or objective of the method

5. How was the method validated?

6. Associated GitHub repository

7. Most recent date of interaction with code repository

Mark only one oval.

- Within the last week
- Within the last month
- Within the last 6 months
- Within the last year
- > 1 year

**KG
Construction
Functionality**

KG construction functionality is evaluated by examining the how well the method covers the steps needed to construct a knowledge graph from scratch and including downloading and processing data (e.g. does the method download data, is it automated, what types of data can be downloaded), building edge lists (e.g. are there options for how edge lists are built), and generating a KG.

8. STEP 1: Does the method include functionality for downloading data?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes - process is NOT automated
- Yes - process is automated
- No
- Maybe
- Other: _____

9. STEP 2: Does the method include functionality for constructing edge lists or sets?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

10. STEP 3: Does the method include functionality for constructing a knowledge graph?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

11. Does the method enable the construction of multiple types of knowledge graphs?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Other: _____

12. Is there any other functionality the method includes related to constructing a knowledge graph? If so, please specify using the "other" option

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Other: _____

13. The method is able to process ontology data.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Other: _____

14. The method is able to process Linked Open Data.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Other: _____

15. The method is able to process experimental data.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Other: _____

16. The method is able to process clinical data.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

17. Other types of data the method is able to process.

18. How many inputs (i.e. data sources) can the method process?

Maturity

Maturity is evaluated by examining the level, stage or development phase of a method.

19. Have there been releases or are there multiple versions of the method?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

20. How many releases have been made?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Beta or Pre-release	<input type="radio"/>	More than 10 releases									

21. Has the method been published?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

22. Do the method developers encourage collaboration?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

23. Are procedures in place to enable collaboration?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

Availability

Availability is evaluated by examining the openness of a method (i.e. license type) and ease of obtaining a copy of the method.

24. Is the method open source?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

25. Method License Type

Mark only one oval.

- No License
- Apache License 2.0
- BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" license
- BSD 2-Clause "Simplified" or "FreeBSD" license
- GNU General Public License (GPL)
- GNU Library or "Lesser" General Public License (LGPL)
- MIT license
- Mozilla Public License 2.0
- Common Development and Distribution License
- Eclipse Public License version 2.0
- Other: _____

26. What operating system can this method be run on?

Check all that apply.

- Linux
 Windows
 Mac OSX
 Cloud-based systems and/or architectures

27. What programming language(s) is the method written in?

Check all that apply.

- Python
 Java
 C or C++
 SQL
 R
 Java Script
 Groovy

Other: _____

28. What external applications does the method depend on?

Usability

Usability is evaluated by examining efforts put in place to ensure that an average user, with reasonable technical skills, could use the method including the quality of documentation, availability of example code and/or sample data as well as operating system and application dependencies.

29. Does the method include a README?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Other: _____

30. Is there a Wiki, Read the Docs, or GitPage associated with the method?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Other: _____

31. Are there examples provided for how to use the method?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other: _____

32. Are any literate programming (e.g. Jupyter Notebook / R Markdown) tutorials provided?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other: _____

33. Are there tools or services to assist with installing the method?

Check all that apply.

The library is available as a package or library (e.g. PyPI, Maven)

Notebook or Markdown Document (e.g. Jupyter Notebook or R Markdown)

Command line script

Other: _____

34. What tools are provided to help run the method (e.g. Docker container, Jupyter Notebook, R Markdown)?

35. Is sample data provided to help explore the method?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other: _____

36. Can the method be run on a variety of different sized data?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other: _____

37. What types of output does the method produce?

Check all that apply.

- OWL or RDF/XML files
- NetworkX Files
- Cytoscape Files
- A text file containing edge lists
- n-triples files

Other: _____

38. Are there indicators of adoption (i.e. repository forks, citations)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

Reproducibility

Reproducibility and maintainability are evaluated by examining whether or not the method provides tools or resources to help reproduce the KG construction process and maintain the code base (e.g. unit testing and continuous integration).

39. What tools are provided to help enable the reproducibility of the method (e.g. Docker container, Jupyter Notebook, R Markdown)?

40. Does the repository include any form of testing?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

41. Does the method utilize continuous integration?

Mark only one oval.

- No
- Yes
- Other: _____

42. Does the method include measures of maintainability?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

43. Is the codebase well-documented?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

44. Does the method repository include (and actively use) an issue tracker?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

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